

School Connectedness as Correlates of Academic Achievement Among In-School Adolescents in Onitsha Education Zone

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Abstract

The study sought to determine how school connectedness correlates to academic achievement among in-school adolescents in Anambra State. The study was guided by four purposes and five research questions. The research design was correlation survey and stratified disproportionate technique was used to select a sample size of 420 students from a population of 14,991 students in secondary schools in Onitsha Education zone, Anambra State. A questionnaire was used to collect data which was administrated through direct delivery approach. Research questions 1 and 2 were analyzed using percentages while Research question 3, 4 and 5 were answered using Product Moment Correlation Coefficient. From the findings, it was obvious that majority of adolescents in secondary schools in Onitsha Education zone rated school connectedness high. The relationship between school connectedness and academic achievement of adolescents in secondary school is high and positive; and the relationship between school connectedness and academic achievement of male and female adolescents in secondary schools is also moderate and positive. Based on the findings, recommendation was made that schools need to work in conjunction with parents to incorporate participative decision making to achieve common goals in adolescents' best interests.

Key words: school connectedness, academic achievement, adolescent

Introduction

The Nigerian society places great emphasis on education achievements because it is believed to be one important avenue for national development. However, it is believed that this can only be achieved if students, especially adolescents in schools, who are in the citadel of learning get actively involved in pursuits of academic excellence. This will, in turn, lead to the technological advancement of the nation. Ricarda, Anja, Anne, Linda (2014) defined academic achievement as a performance outcome that indicates the extent to which a person has accomplished specific goals that were the focus of activities in instructional environments, specifically in school, college and University.

Also Kyoshaba(2009) posited that the role of academic achievement as one of the predictors of one's life success, in the aspects of academic placement in schools to higher educational institutions as well as the level employability in one's career is inevitable. No wonder Chapman (2010) stated that high academic achievement predicts students' high level of marketability, enabling them to choose their own placement. Academic achievement is considered to be the formal demonstration of learning (including knowledge, understanding and thinking skills) attained by a student as measured by standardized academic achievement tests. For example, knowledge and ability in the areas of reading, language, and mathematics are included (Brain & Ray, 2010).

According to Marc, Maria, Peter and Susan (2012), the effective, lasting academic achievement is built on caring relationships and warm but challenging classroom and school environments. Therefore parents, schools and communities all need to work together to create an environment that facilitates healthy development of adolescents. If students do not feel a sense of belonging at school, they may not feel connected to the school and this may lower their likelihood to focus or be engaged in the learning process.

Students feel more connected to their school when they believe that the adults and other students at school not only care about how well they are learning, but also being valued as individuals. Those who feel connected to school are more likely to succeed academically and make healthy choices. No wonder Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (2008) stated that students who do well academically are less likely to engage in risky behaviours compared to students with low grades. Also students with higher grade are less likely to carry dangerous weapons, smoke cigarettes, drink alcohol and have risky sexual intercourse. The students are likely to perform better in the classroom when they feel more connected to school. Just as societal interactions impact the success of adults in the working world, the school atmosphere impacts students' ability to be academically successful. For instance, the significant time students have with teachers in school, and the quality of students' relationships with teachers is a critical influence on their social, emotional, and academic development (Wentzel, 2009). Students' academic achievement therefore may be a direct result of dynamic interactions occurring between individuals in their social contexts.

School connectedness has an impact on other aspects of life including school behaviours, attendance and involvement, as well as potential to engage in behaviours that may compromise one's health. Furthermore, the presence of physical expression, relational expression and victimization in schools has also been linked to school connectedness and the higher the presence of these destructive forces, the lower the feeling of school connectedness may be among students. As Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (2008) noted, central to students' connection to school is a physically and emotionally safe environment.

School connectedness could be developed through consistent communication between teachers and students whereby teachers present unequivocal goals for the learning process and consistent

classroom expectations and routines. Teachers have an amazing and extraordinary opportunity to connect with students and to enhance their school experiences (Mary & John, 2014).

Furthermore as observed by Mary and John, the idea of adult support whereby schools can form schools within a school, or create multidisciplinary teams of teachers in which a small number of teachers know each student and can ensure that every student has an identified advisor can increase school connectedness. Also, according to Jim (2010) teachers need to involve students in activities that traditionally involve only adults, for instance, Parent-teacher conferences, curriculum selection committees, school health teams. Also students need to be engaged in appropriate leadership positions in the classroom and provide avenues for their voices and opinions to be heard. It is important that both students and adults are committed to learning and are involved in school activities.

Moreover, Andy and Tommy (2013) stated that engaging students in planning for their future including career and personal goals assists them in mapping out steps to take to meet their goals and opening up the possibility for socialization and stronger relationships with students. This idea was further espoused by Education Development Centre (2008) when it stated the need to encourage school staff to make concerted effort in reaching out to students who may be experiencing academic or social issues and get to know them, use various of teaching methods such as discussion questions, extra readings and group projects to foster critical and reflective thinking, problem-solving skills and a supportive psychosocial climate during teaching and learning.

However, students tend to differ in terms of gender. Gender (Male and Female) here is said to have been a major factor when it comes to students' connectedness to school activities and as well as their academic achievement. Weiss and Uzoma (2015) opined that gender is a varied socially and culturally constructed roles, qualities, and behaviours that are ascribed to men and women of different societies. Gender refers to the attitudes feelings and behaviours that a given culture associate with a person's biological self (American Psychological Association, 2012). Furthermore, Udoukpong, Emah, and Umoren (2012) found that students' gender do contribute to academic achievement in school learning. Nevertheless, the researcher seeks to find out the relationship existing between school connectedness and the academic achievement of male and female students in secondary schools.

It is the belief of the researchers that academic achievement would be improved upon if some factors were adequately addressed. Since achievement plays an important role in the lives and activities of students, it is necessary to investigate issues that surround it and provide how best to obtain this highly desired achievement. This study therefore is geared toward finding out whether school connectedness correlate with the academic achievement of secondary school adolescents in Anambra State.

Purpose of the study

The purpose of this study is to find out the relationship between school connectedness and academic achievement of secondary school adolescents in Anambra State precisely Onitsha Educational Zone. Specifically the study seeks to find out:

1. School connectedness scores of secondary school adolescents in Onitsha Educational Zone.
2. Academic achievement scores of secondary school adolescents in English language in Onitsha Educational Zone.
3. The relationship between school connectedness and academic achievement of secondary school adolescents in English language.
4. The relationship between school connectedness and academic achievement of male and female adolescents in secondary schools in English language.

Research Questions

1. What are school connectedness scores of adolescents?
2. What are the academic achievement scores of secondary school adolescents in English language?
3. What is the relationship between school connectedness and academic achievement of secondary school adolescents in English language?
4. What is the relationship between school connectedness and academic achievement in English language of female adolescents in secondary schools?
5. What is the relationship between school connectedness and academic achievement in English language of male adolescents in secondary schools?

Method

The research design for this study is correlational research design. A correlational survey design is considered appropriate for this study because it seeks to establish a relationship between two or more variables (Nworgu, 2015). The study was conducted in Onitsha Education zone, Anambra state. The population of this study comprised of 14,991 which involves all the students in the Onitsha Education zone, Anambra State (Anambra State Post Primary School Service Commission, Awka, 2015).

The sample for the study is 420 students. Firstly, simple random sampling was employed in selecting 10 schools from the 31 secondary schools in the zone. Secondly, disproportionate stratified random sampling was further employed to choose 42 students from each of the already selected schools in the area.

The instrument for the study is a questionnaire which has 3 sections; section A, B and C. Section A is personal data of the respondents; Section B is titled "School Connectedness Questionnaire (SCQ)" for the students. Section C is the Academic Achievement scores in English language. The instrument was later subjected to face validity and the reliability of the instrument established using Cronbach Alpha statistics where 20 questionnaire copies were distributed to SS2 students from schools in Delta State through purposive sampling technique in a trial testing to establish the reliability of the instrument.

The administration of the instrument for data collection was done through direct delivery approach. By this method, copies of the questionnaire were distributed personally to the respondents by the researcher with the help of two briefed research assistants. The data relating to research questions 1 and 2 were analyzed using aggregate scores and percentages, research questions 3 to 5 were analyzed using Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (Pearson r). The scores of the teacher-made test, comprising the performance grades of the students on English language and indicating their achievements in schools were reported as aggregate scores as follows:

70 – 100 = Very good achievement

50 – 69 = Good achievement

0 – 49 = Poor achievement.

The decision rule for judging the resulting correlation coefficient was that:

Low relationship = +0.00 – 0.39

Moderate relationship = +0.40 – 0.69

High relationship = +0.70 – 1.00

So also the decision rule for school connectedness was:

Low connectedness- 20.00-35.00

High connectedness- 36.00-57.00

Very High Connectedness- 58.00-80.00

Results

Analyses of data are hereby presented in tables as shown below.

Research Question 1:

What are school connectedness scores of adolescents?

Table 1: *Range of scores and percentages on adolescents' school connectedness*

Range of Scores	N	%	Remarks
20.00 to 35.00	70	13.31	Low school connectedness
36.00 to 55.00	236	63.40	High school connectedness
58.00 to 80.00	134	23.29	Very Highschool connectedness

Table 1 reveals that 70 (13.31%) out of 420 the students rated their school connectedness Low by scoring between 20.00 and 35.00, while 236 (63.40%) of the students who scored between 36.00 and 55.00 rated their school connectedness High. Also, 134 (23.29%) of the students who scored between 58.00 and 80.00 rated their school connectedness Very high.

Research Question 2

What are the academic achievement scores of secondary school students in English?

Table 2: *Range of Grades of the Participants in English Language*

Grade Range	Frequencies	Percentage
A = 4 – Very high	60	11.36%
B = 3 – High	120	23.64%
C = 2 – Moderate	184	45.00%
D = 1 – Low	76	20.00%
Total	420	100%

Source: *Schools Record, from form-masters and form-mistresses*

As shown in table 2 above, students' grade were obtained at the time of data collection ($n=420$). This grades were converted to numerical points with grades A – E being represented with numerical values of 0 – 4. The table revealed that 60(11.36%) of the students scored A, 120(23.64%) scored B, 184(45.00%) scored C, while a total of 76(20.00%) scored D.

Research Question 3

What is the relationship between school connectedness scores and academic achievement of secondary school students?

Table 3: *Pearson r on the adolescents' school connectedness and academic achievement of students*

N	R	Remark
420	0.65	Moderate positive relationship

Table 3 reveals that there is moderate positive relationship of 0.65 existing between adolescent's school connectedness and academic achievement of secondary school students.

Research Question 4

What is the relationship between school connectedness scores and academic achievement of male secondary school students?

Table 4: *Pearson r on the school connectedness and academic achievement of male secondary school students*

N	R	Remark
420	0.56	Moderate positive relationship

Table 4 indicates that there is Moderate positive relationship of 0.56 existing between school connectedness and academic achievement of male secondary school students.

Research Question 5

What is the relationship between school connectedness scores and academic achievement of female secondary school students?

Table 5: *Pearson r on the school connectedness and academic achievement of female secondary school students*

N	R	Remark
420	0.66	Moderate positive relationship

Table 5 indicates that there is Moderate positive relationship of 0.66 existing between school connectedness and academic achievement of female secondary school students.

Discussion

Findings from this study reveals; that most adolescents (63.40%) in secondary schools rated their school connectedness high, while some of these adolescents (13.31%) and (23.29%) rated their school connectedness Low and Very High respectively. The study further reveals that the relationship between school connectedness and academic achievement of adolescents in secondary schools is Moderate and positive. These findings agreed with Odeh,Oguche, Angelina and Ivagher (2015), and Adekunle (2014). The findings of these studies showed that students with high school connectedness achieved academically higher than those with low school connectedness.

Similarly, this study also agree with the finding of Agu, Omenyi and Odimegwu (2010) whose study noted that several students who seemed to have low school connectedness levels scored highest on academic achievement. Based on his finding, he concluded that other factors seem to be negatively affecting successful students' school connectedness.

Furthermore, this finding reveals that relationship between school connectedness and academic achievement of male and female adolescents in secondary school is moderate and positive. This is in line with the findings of Chohan and Khan (2010) which noted that academic achievement was excellent among boys and girls with high school connectedness, and that school connectedness is significantly related to academic achievement.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of this study, the following conclusions are made: majority of adolescents in secondary schools in Onitsha Education Zone rates school connectedness high. The relationship between school connectedness and academic achievement of adolescents in secondary schools is moderate and positive. And, the relationship between school connectedness and academic achievement of male and female adolescents in secondary school is moderate and positive.

Implication of the Study

Based on the findings of the study, the following implications of the study were noted.

The findings thus creates awareness that teachers, who wish to educate their students, cannot just rely on school learning but need to totally involve them in school decisions making so as to be fully part of the school activities as well as their parents in making the needed progress.

Findings from the study could stimulate the parents to see the need to start thinking towards creating a better home environment that encourages learning, and became more involved in their children education both at school and in the community.

The school and education authorities need to offer opportunities for parents to be introduced to and review any subject matter which may be covered in class so that they become comfortable with the subject and will be willing to engage their child. This will likely help the child become confident that the parent can provide proper assistance when needed.

More so, the education authorities will see the need to put school-based programs and policies in place that will address the specific factors that contribute to or detract students from school connectedness.

Recommendation

Based on the findings of the study, it was therefore recommended that:

The study has shown that school connectedness promotes belongingness, cohesiveness, security and motivates adolescents to persevere regardless of challenges. Thus, schools need to work in conjunction with parents to incorporate participative decision making to achieve common goals in adolescents' best interests. This fosters the value of education and reinforces parental roles in initiating learning activities at home to improve students' performance in at school.

Reference

- Adekunle, O.S. (2014). School connectedness, emotional intelligence and locus of control as determinants of academic achievement among school going adolescents in Ikeja, Lagos State. *Journal of Educational Policy and Entrepreneurial Research (JEPER)*, 1(3), 9-17.
- Agu, N., Omenyi, A., & Odimegwu, C. (2010). An assessment of students' connectedness in tertiary institutions in Anambra State of Nigeria. *Educational Research and Reviews*, 5(2), 090-098.
- American Psychological Association, (2012). *Definition of term: Gender*. Retrieved on December, 2016 from <http://www.apa.org/pi/lgbt/resources/sexuality-definitions.pdf>
- Andy, C. & Tommy, D. (2013). *A roadmap for transforming the college-to-career experience*. Retrieved from <http://rethinkingsuccess.wfu.edu/files/2013/05/A-Roadmap-for-Transforming-The-College-to-Career-Experience.pdf>
- Brian, D. & Ray, G. (2010). Academic achievement and demographic traits of home-school students: A nationwide study. *Journal of Research and Reflections in Education*, 8(1) 20-24.
- Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (2008). *Fact sheet: Health risk behaviors and academic achievement*. Atlanta: U.S. Department of Health and Human Services.
- Chapman, E. (2010). Alternative approaches to assessing student engagement rates. *Practical Assessment, Research & Evaluation*, 8(13). Retrieved from <http://PAREonline.net/getvn.asp?v=8&n=13>
- Chohan, B.I., & Khan, R.M. (2010). Impact of parental support on the academic performance and self-concept of the student. *Journal of Research and Reflections in Education*, 4(1), 14 -26.
- Clark, L.F., Miller, K.S., & Nagy, S.S. (2005). Adult identity mentoring: Reducing sexual risk for African-American seventh grade students. *Journal of Adolescent Health* 37(4), 337-337.
- Hill, N.E., & Chao, R.K. (2009). *Families, schools, and the adolescent: Connecting research, policy, and practice*. New York: Teachers College Press.
- Jim, E. (2010). *Using active learning instructional strategies to create excitement and enhance learning*. Florida, U.S: Department of Adult, career & higher education.
- Kyoshaba, M. (2009). Factors affecting academic performance of undergraduate students at Uganda Christian University. Retrieved on Oct 26 2017 from *social media and academic performance of students (PDF Download Available)*. Available from: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/273765340_social_media_and_academic_performance_of_students].
- Marc, A.B., Maria, R.R., Peter, S. & Susan, E.R. (2012). Enhancing academic performance and social and emotional competence with the ruler feeling words curriculum. *Journal of learning and individual differences*, 22(2), 218-224.
- Mary, B.W. & John, F.S. (2014). *Simple and complex post-traumatic stress disorder: Strategies for comprehensive treatment in clinical practice*. New York: [education.gsu.edu/schoolsafety/download%20files/wp%202002%20school % 20 climate. pdf](http://education.gsu.edu/schoolsafety/download%20files/wp%202002%20school%20climate.pdf).

- McCellan, E.R. (2007). *Selected demographic factors, adolescent self-concept as a future music educator, and the decision to major in music education*. Retrieved from :<http://library.uncg.edu/>
- Nwogu, B. G. (2015). *Educational Research: Basic Issues and Methodology* (3rd Ed.). Enugu. University Trust Publishers.
- Odeh. R. C., Oguche, O., Angelina. M., & Ivagher, E.D. (2015). Influence of school environment on academic achievement of students in secondary schools in zone “a” senatorial district of Benue State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Recent Scientific Research*, 6(7), 4914-4922.
- Patton, G.C., Bond, L., Carlin, J.B., Thomas, L., Butler, H., Glover, S. ... Bowes, G. (2006). Promoting social inclusion in schools: A randomized trial of effects on student health risk behaviour and well-being. *American Journal of Public Health* 96(9), 1582-1587.
- Ricarda, S., Anja, M., Anne, F. & Linda, W. (2014). Gender differences in school success: What are the roles of students' intelligence, personality and motivation? *Educational Research*, 56(2), 230–243, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/00131881.2014.898917>
- Udoukpong, B. E., Emah, I. E., & Umoren, S. E. (2012). Business studies academic performance differences of secondary school juniors in Akwa Ibom State of Nigeria. *International Education Studies*, 5(2), 45-50.
- Waiss, G. & Uzoma, O. F. (2015). Effect of cooperative learning strategies on achievement motivation of low achieving students in reading comprehension. *Unpublished M.Ed Thesis* University of Nigeria, Nsukka.
- Walter, J. (2012) Correlational Research. Retrieved August 14, 2012 from: www.capilanou.ca/programs/psychology/students/research/correlation.html